

AN ATTEMPT TO CORRELATE THE CONSTITUTION OF GLASS WITH THE POTENTIAL AT GLASS-ELECTROLYTE INTERFACES.

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The *E. M. F.* of cells in which powdered glass in contact with potassium silicate solutions of different concentrations formed one component was measured, the other components being normal calomel and calcium amalgam electrodes. Powdered glass has been found to behave as a sparingly soluble salt. An attempt has been made to correlate the results obtained with the constitution of glass.

If glass be considered a definite compound, a saturated solution of powdered soft glass in water will furnish definite amounts of sodium, calcium and silicate ions and will conform to a definite solubility product value. If now a solution of potassium silicate be in contact with powdered glass and be saturated with it, an equilibrium will be set up among the sodium, calcium and silicate ions, for the concentrations of which the law of mass action will apply. The bulk of the silicate and the concentrations of the cations will be controlled by the concentration of the silicate ion through the solubility product of glass. The system is thus comparable with a solution of potassium chloride in contact with mercurous chloride and saturated with it, the concentrations of the cations in both the cases being controlled through variations in the concentrations of the anions. It would thus be possible to set up an electrode of the second type if one of the cation metals of glass be put in contact with a solution of potassium silicate in contact with powdered glass and saturated with it. Owing, however, to the unstable nature of the cation metals of glass, amalgam electrodes will have to be used.

In the present experiments a cell has been set up on the above principle, and the variations in the *E. M. F.* of the cell for different concentrations of the potassium silicate solution have been measured. On the basis of certain assumptions, it is possible to derive an expression which connects the *E. M. F.* of the cell with the constitution of glass. This expression has been applied to the experimental values to get information about the possible constitution of glass considered as a compound.

Derivation of the Expression for the E. M. F.

Considering the cell,

the E. M. F. of the cell is given by the expression

$$e_1 = E_{\text{Calomel}} - \left\{ E^\circ_{\text{Ca}^{++}} + \frac{RT}{nF} \log [\text{Ca}^{++}] \right\} \quad \dots (i)$$

where $E^\circ_{\text{Ca}^{++}}$ represents the normal potential of calcium ions. Let the glass have a composition, $\frac{x}{2} \text{Na}_2\text{O}$, $y \text{CaO}$, $z \text{SiO}_2$. On ionisation we get

By applying the law of mass action we get:

$$[\text{Na}^+]^x [\text{Ca}^{++}]^y [\text{Silicate}^{--}]^z = K$$

$$\text{or} \quad [\text{Na}^+]^x [\text{Ca}^{++}]^y = \frac{K}{[\text{Silicate}^{--}]^z} \quad \dots (ii)$$

Let $\frac{x}{y} = p$, i.e., for every calcium ion furnished by the ionisation of the glass in a saturated solution, let p ions of sodium be obtained. Thus in a saturated solution of glass,

$$[\text{Na}^+] = p [\text{Ca}^{++}].$$

Substituting this value in equation (ii) we get,

$$p^x \cdot [\text{Ca}^{++}]^x \cdot [\text{Ca}^{++}]^y = \frac{K}{[\text{Silicate}^{--}]^z}$$

$$\text{or} \quad [\text{Ca}^{++}] = \left\{ \frac{K}{p^x} \cdot \frac{1}{[\text{Silicate}^{--}]^z} \right\}^{\frac{1}{(x+y)}}$$

Substituting this value for the calcium ion concentration in equation (i) we get

$$e_1 = E_{\text{Calomel}} - \left\{ E^\circ_{\text{Ca}^{++}} + \frac{RT}{nF} \cdot \frac{1}{(x+y)} \cdot \log \left(\frac{K}{p^x} \cdot \frac{1}{[\text{Silicate}^{--}]^z} \right) \right\}$$

$$\text{or } e_1 = E_{\text{Calomel}} - E^\circ_{\text{Ca}^{++}} - \frac{1}{(x+y)} \cdot \frac{RT}{nF} \log \frac{K}{p^x} + \frac{z}{(x+y)} \cdot \frac{RT}{nF} \log [\text{Silicate}^{--}] C_1$$

Next consider an exactly similar cell but with a different concentration of potassium silicate solution = C_2 . viz.,

As before the e. m. f. of this cell will be given by

$$e_2 = E_{\text{Calomel}} - E^{\circ}_{\text{Ca}^{++}} - \frac{x}{(x+y)} \cdot \frac{RT}{nF} \log \frac{K}{p^x} + \frac{z}{(x+y)} \cdot \frac{RT}{nF} \log [\text{Silicate}^{--}]_{C_2}$$

Therefore,

$$e_1 - e_2 = \frac{z}{(x+y)} \cdot \frac{RT}{nF} \cdot \left\{ \log [\text{silicate ion}]_{C_1} - \log [\text{silicate ion}]_{C_2} \right\}$$

$$\text{or} \quad e_1 - e_2 = \frac{z}{(x+y)} \cdot \frac{RT}{nF} \cdot \log \frac{[\text{silicate ion}]_{C_1}}{[\text{silicate ion}]_{C_2}} \quad \dots \text{ (iii)}$$

The above expression has been applied to the present experiments.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

A sample of glass was prepared by fusing together sodium carbonate, lime and silica. Pure anhydrous sodium carbonate (40 g.), dry calcium carbonate (11 g.) and washed precipitated silica (75 g.) were intimately mixed together. The mixture was charged into fire-clay crucibles and heated for 3-4 hours in an electric furnace which gave a temperature of about 1000-1100°. The resulting sample of glass was finely powdered and stocked for use during subsequent experiments.

The exact composition of the above sample of glass was determined by analysis which gave the following percentage values (Na₂O, 21.8; CaO, 6.0; SiO₂, 72.2) corresponding approximately to an analytical composition, 3Na₂O, CaO.10 SiO₂.

The calcium amalgam used during the measurements was prepared by the method recommended by Neuhausen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 1445). Sufficient quantity of pure mercury was placed in a flat-bottomed glass basin so as to just cover up the bottom of the vessel. A large cathode surface without using too much mercury is desirable. A 1.75M solution of calcium chloride was poured over the mercury to form a layer about 2 cm. high. A perforated circular disc of platinum of 15 sq. cm. surface area served as the anode. The anode was adjusted at the proper height and the electrolysis was carried out with a current of 3.5 amps. After the amalgam had been formed, the solution was drained off, the surface of the amalgam was wiped with a dry filter paper, and it was then quickly transferred to a stoppered vessel and preserved in an atmosphere of nitrogen.

Neuhausen has recommended an atmosphere of carbon dioxide for preserving the amalgam. In the present experiments an inert atmosphere of nitrogen has been found more suitable as carbon dioxide cannot be used where measurements with alkali silica solutions are concerned.

FIG. 1.

The experimental arrangement for the cell is based on the apparatus recommended by Fosbinder (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1349). Certain necessary modifications have been introduced. The arrangement is shown diagrammatically in Fig. 1. Nitrogen from a six litre aspirator bottle was allowed to stream through a series of bubblers (1, 2, 3) containing concentrated ferrous sulphate solution and alkaline pyrogallol. With the help of the taps t_1 and t_2 , the nitrogen could bubble directly into the solution in the experimental tube or through G_3 and the capillary tube, as desired. Potassium silicate solution of requisite concentration was thoroughly shaken up with the powdered glass and filled into the experimental tube. The same solution was also put in the globe G_2 . The vessels marked G contained solid powdered glass and served to maintain the solution saturated with respect to glass. The amalgam was contained in the globe G_2 and was allowed to enter the solution in the experimental tube through the capillary. During its passage the amalgam swept over the platinum wire (Pt) which served as the terminal at the amalgam end of the cell. C was a normal calomel electrode. By regulating the flow of liquids from G_1 and G_2 , the junction was constantly renewed and the junction potential was

considerably minimised. The potential was measured through the leads L_1 and L_2 , by means of a Tinsley potentiometer.

The cell set up was

and the E. M. F. with potassium silicate solutions of different concentrations were measured. The potassium silicate used was a sample of Kahlbaum's metasilicate. The average E. M. F. values of several runs are given in the following tables.

It should be mentioned that considerable difficulty was encountered in protecting the amalgam and stopping it from choking the capillary. The difficulty, however, was overcome to a large extent by maintaining a slight regulated pressure of nitrogen through the globe G_2 . With each concentration of potassium silicate solution, a large number of E. M. F. readings were taken and only those values which agreed closely within a few millivolts have been utilised.

Freezing points of potassium silicate solutions have been determined by Kahlenburg and Lincoln (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1898, 2, 77). Attempts were made to determine the activity coefficients of potassium silicate solutions from these data by using the Lewis and Linhart formula (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 1952). Owing, however, to the doubtful nature of the value of ν , the number of ions furnished on dissociation, the results were not satisfactory. An accurate series of conductivity measurements of sodium silicate solutions have been made by Harman (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1155). These data have been used to calculate the degree of dissociation of potassium silicate solutions, the values for the sodium and potassium salts being taken as comparable. The degrees of dissociation reckoned in the above manner are given in Table I. In Table II are given the values of

$(e_1 - e_2)$ and the corresponding values of $\left(\frac{z}{x+y}\right)$ as calculated with the help of equation (iii).

Pot. silicate soln.	TABLE I.			TABLE II.		
	$\alpha = \frac{\Lambda_{\nu}}{\Lambda_{\infty}}$	[Silicate ⁻]	Cell.	$e_1 - e_2$.	$\frac{z}{x+y}$	
1.00 N	0.5	0.5	$e_N - e_{0.1N}$	0.043 volt.	1.79	
0.10	0.812	0.081	$e_N - e_{0.02N}$	0.027	2.18	
0.04	0.91	0.036	$e_N - e_{0.01N}$	0.082	1.19	
0.02	0.95	0.019	$e_{0.1N} - e_{0.02N}$	0.012	1.76	
0.01	0.97	0.0097	$e_{0.1N} - e_{0.01N}$	0.061	2.40	

DISCUSSION.

The experimental results show that powdered glass behaves as a sparingly soluble salt. When glass is dissolved in water, it furnishes calcium ions which can function to a large extent as reversible ions in an electrode process. Those facts support the view that pure glass is a true chemical compound.

A considerable difference of opinion exists as to the chemical composition of glasses, which are generally regarded as a complex mixture of several simple silicates or a solid solution. The results of a study of durability of soda-lime-silica glasses towards chemical reagents led some investigators to postulate the existence of a compound, $6\text{SiO}_2 \cdot \text{CaO} \cdot \text{Na}_2\text{O}$. The work of Foerster (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1894, 38, 381) on the action of water on vessels of various kinds of glasses showed that minimum corrosion occurred with the glass of approximately the $6\text{SiO}_2 \cdot \text{R}'' \text{O} \cdot \text{M}'_2\text{O}$ composition. This particular composition has frequently been referred to in literature as the "normal glass". From the results of analyses of a large number of glasses and Foerster's experiments, Zulkowski (*Chem. Ind.*, 1899, 22, 280) came to the conclusion that there must be a definite complex silicate in glass of composition stated above, and ascribed to it the formula,

A complex compound of the composition, $6\text{SiO}_2 \cdot \text{CaO} \cdot \text{Na}_2\text{O}$, will give both sodium and calcium ions in solution, and, when the complex is broken down, the ratio of silica ions (z) to the sum of calcium (x) and sodium (y) ions will be equal to 2. The results in Table II show that the ratio $z : (x + y)$ is fairly constant, and the average value of the ratio is 2:1. It is not likely that the ratio will have the same value in all cases if glass were a mixture of simple silicates.

Further experiments with sodium amalgam and an improved method for elimination of liquid junction are being attempted.

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